

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF LEUCORRHEA (*SHWETPRADAR*) – A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda has two main objectives one is to maintain the positive health & second is to eradicate the disease. *Shwetpradar* (i.e Leucorrhea) also known as vaginal white discharge is one of the common condition seen in Gynaecological practice by women of all ages. It may be due to various causes like Pelvic Inflammatory diseases, fungal infections, cervicitis, anemia, diabetes etc. It is a non pathological symptom secondary to inflammatory conditions of vagina or cervix & wants no medical interventions but it is significant if it is profuse, foul smelling, change in its colour & consistency & blood stained. In Ayurveda, *Yonivyapad* which are caused by *kapha* or *vata-kaphaja* doshas are causative factor of *shwetpradar*. This Case Study presents successful management of a 34 year old patient suffering from Chronic leucorrhea. The Patient underwent effective treatment through which involved the administration of a therapeutic combination of *abhyantar chikitsa* along with *sthanik chikitsa* of *Yonidhawan*.

KEYWORDS: *Shwetpradar*, leucorrhea, *Yonidhawan*.

• INTRODUCTION

In the Chaos of Women's life her health is often neglected. Along with overall health, at different stages of women's lives from puberty to menopause a healthy reproductive system should also be maintained. Today infection associated with *Yoni* is a common problem regardless of age or status. Normal physiological vaginal discharge may appear clear or cloudy white & should not have any odour or cause local irritation. Changes in the consistency, colour, amount or smell of vaginal discharge may indicate Vulvovaginal infection or other underlying conditions of Genital tract.

Shwetpradar is described in ancient Ayurvedic texts such as *Sharangdhara Samhita*, *Bhavprakash* & *Yogratmakar*. In *Charak Samhita*, the management of *shwetpradar* is detailed under description of *Pandura Asrigdara*. *Chakrapani* explained the term *Pandura Asrigdara* as *Shwetpradar* in his commentary on *Charak Samhita*, Also *Shwetpradar* or *Yonisrava* is mentioned as symptom in various other diseases also.

Based on the clinical features *Shwetpradar* can be considered as a *Kaphaja* disorder in region of *Apana*

vayu. As any type of *Strava* (discharge) is a result of *Kapha dosha*, it can be said that vitiated *kapha*, along with various factor leads to white vaginal discharge due to *Rasa dushti* caused by *kapha*.

In this Case Study with use of combined therapy of *sthanik chikitsa* & *shaman chikitsa* the disease has been cured.

• AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Aim – To Study effect of *Sthanik Chikitsa* in *Shwetpradar*.

Objectives

To Study efficacy of *Yonidhawan*.

To Study *Shwetpradar* (leucorrhea) in detail.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Case Description

A 34 year old female patient came to OPD with complaints of *Yonigata Shvet srava* (vaginal white discharge), *Katishool* (low bachache), *Yonikandu* (itching at vulva), *Daurgandhya* (odour) since last 7-8 months.

Patient has taken allopathy treatment for 3-4 months but got temporary relief then patient came to Y.M.T Ayurvedic Hospital for further management.

Past Medical History – No h/o DM/HTN/Bronchial Asthma/Hypotension.

Past Surgical History – No h/o any surgical illness.

Past H/o Allergy – No any.

Family History – Nil.

Menarche – 14 years

LMP –

She had regular menses at interval of 28-36 days, last for 4-5 days

Married since 8 years

Coital History – 2 times/week

Contraceptive History – No contraception used by partner

Obs/history – P2L2A0D0

P1 – 6yr, FTND

P2 – 3yr, FTND

Menstrual History

General Examination

GC – stable

T – Afebrile

P – 80/min

BP – 120/70mmhg

Systemic Examination

RS – AEBE, Clear

CVS – S1S2, Normal

CNS – conscious, oriented

GIT – soft, NT

Per Speculum/Per Vaginal Examination

White thick curdy discharge, foul smelling, mild cervical erosion.

Uterus AV, B/L fornices nontender.

• Assessment Criteria

1. *Shweta Srava* (Vaginal White Discharge)

No Vaginal Discharge – 0

Mild (Occasionally wetting of undergarments / slight discharge) – 1

Moderate (wetting of undergarments) – 2

Severe (Heavy discharge which need vulval pads) – 3

2. *Katishoola* (Backache)

No Pain – 0

Mild (Can withstand pain & can manage routine work) – 1

Moderate (Cannot manage routine work & need to take rest) – 2

Severe (Cannot withstand pain & need treatment) – 3

3. *Yonikandu* (Itching of vulva)

No Itching – 0

Mild (Slight rub) – 1

Moderate (Instant rub causing redness) – 2

Severe (Continuous rub causing redness) – 3

4. *Durgandha* (Odour)

Absent – 0

Mild – 1

Moderate – 2

Severe – 3

• Treatment Protocol

Combined treatment of *Sthanik chikitsa* & *Abhyantara Chikitsa* has been continues taken for 3 months

Sthanik Chikitsa – (3 Consecutive cycles after menses)

<i>Lodhra vata twak Kashaya</i>	<i>Yoniprakshalana</i> Twice a day	15 days
<i>Triphala Varti</i>	<i>YoniVarti</i> Once a day	7 days

Abhyantar Chikitsa

Medicine	Dosage	Duration
<i>Pushyanug Churna</i> 1gm <i>Lodhra Churna</i> 1gm <i>Amalaki Churna</i> 1gm	BD (AF with Rice water / tandulodaka)	15 days
<i>Lodhrasava</i> 10ml	BD (AF with water)	15 days

Pathya – Patient was instructed to avoid extra oily food items, outside snacks, salty food etc. Also advised to maintain her personal hygiene & avoid common toilets.

• RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Shwetpradara is a common gynaecological problem seen in patients of all age groups. Majority of patients usually

ignore these problems due to embarrassment or sometimes due to busy life till it hampers daily routine.

1. *Lodhra vata twak kashaya* – *Lodhra* & *Vata* possessing *Kapha-Pitta Sthamabaka* properties indicated in *Shwetpradar*. *Lodhra* is *kapha pittaghna* & *Kashaya Rasatmaka, laghu, Shita, Snigdha, Katu Vipaki* &

Stambhaka, Balya, Raktapittahara & indicated in *Pradara*. *Vata* is *kapha-pittaghna* & having *Yonidoshara* properties, *Kashaya rasatmaka, Guru, Shita, Snigdha, Katu Vipaki* & *Stambhaka, balya, Raktapittahara* & indicated in *Pradara*. *Lodhra* & *Vata* have *laghu, ruksha guna* which contributes to effect of *sthambhana* & *shoshana* of Drava or Vaginal Discharge. *Lodhra* & *Vata* posses astringent property which is attributed to flavonoids & tannins. *Lodhra* mainly contains flavonoids, having properties like anti-inflammatory, anti oxidant, immunomodulatory, antibacterial, antiparasitics & antiviral properties. *Vata* attributes tannis which can also be used as adhesive, biocide & fungicide.

2. *Triphala Varti* – *Triphala* constituents properties like *Tridoshaghna, shothahara* (anti-inflammatory), *Krimighna* (antimicrobials), *Vrana shodhak, Vrana ropak, Raktaprasadak, lekhana, Sthambhana* these properties makes it ideal for *Yonikandu* & *Yonirava*.

3. *Pushyanug Churna* - It has properties like *stambhan* & indicated in various vaginal discharges & *Jantukrita doshas*.

4. *Amalaki* is *Rasayana*, supports healthy metabolism & is anti inflammatory.

5. *Lodhrasava* – Due to its *stambhaka* & *Kashaya* properties naturally absorb excess moisture (*kleda*) and regulate vaginal fluids.

- Follow Ups – (Gradations of parameters at follow-up)

Assesment Criteria	Day 1	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90
<i>Shwetsrava</i>	3	2	1	1	1	0	0
<i>Katishoola</i>	3	2	2	1	1	1	0
<i>Yonikandu</i>	3	2	1	1	0	0	0
<i>Daurgandha</i>	3	2	1	0	0	0	0

CONCLUSION

Shwetpradar mentioned in Ayurvedic literature & leucorrhoea mentioned in modern Gynaecology closely resemble with each other.

Personal hygiene & following proper dietary regimen are helpful to prevent *Shwetpradar*.

The Drugs which are having predominance of *kashaya rasa, Kapha shamak* & *sthambaka* properties should be used in treatment of *Shwetpradar*.

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